

The Effectiveness of Distance Teaching Methods for Applied Materials for Design and Visual Communication Departments in Jordan: An Experimental Research at Jadara Private University

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 04, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Applied Learning, Distance-Learning, Learning-Methods, Visual-Communication</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6329807</p>	<p><i>This paper highlights the influence of distance- learning methods - which are followed by the Visual communication schools in Jordan - on the outcome of applied learning, since the start of Covid-19 pandemic in March 2020 until today. Where the efficiency of the study count on measuring the efficacy of distance learning methods and tools through students. Though the effectiveness of mutual learning that "Design Thinking" suggests. The researchers adapt an empirical research that relies on monitoring experiment. The study was performed using a convenience sample of 40 male/female student's (ages 18 and 22) in Jadara University. The findings revealed that there were statistically significant differences between the experimental and the control groups, in favor of the experimental and the experimental group's attitudes were also more positive towards the using of Design Thinking methods in learning, the researchers Provide a range of recommendations for educators in the field, it goals to have an effective academic development plans and training which can be achieved by implementing an official training courses of teaching methods in advanced that meets the requirements of distance learning.</i></p>

Introduction

The advantage of the scientific and technological revolution that the world is witnessing today is that the impact of knowledge on economic and social life and human lifestyle has increased. Knowledge and information have become a major economic resource, but rather a new strategic resource that complements natural resources. Access to the era of knowledge is based on the exploitation of modern technologies in various aspects of contemporary life. The entire world has become a small village, and the Internet has transcended or cancels geographical and regional borders, and erases isolation with amazing and multiple benefits that play an essential and prominent role in our lives. It became a new method that jumped with different knowledge and sciences from the limited to the comprehensive, and modern communication became characterized as electronic communication. Technology today is the raw material for modern and future life, and by it nations are differentiated. Darwin's statement "survival of the fittest", which ruled many of the ideological and economic divisions of the world before, has outdated; To become a future "survival of knowledge". We find that countries are classified by this criterion into advanced, developing and underdeveloped; The first owned the reins of science, knowledge, technology and technology, the second was limited to its application and use, and the third was still in the role of a spectator, and this is the greatest challenge, and no nation will move from one stage to another except with its educational curricula, curricula, and methods of teaching and learning (Hawamdeh, 2011).

The challenges created by the COVID-19 pandemic in education are the hallmark of our time, and these changes imposed new educational patterns that depend heavily on the introduction of technology in the field of education, so educational institutions must change their methods, as distance education has continued since March of last year 2020 until today, and it was a sufficient period to measure the effectiveness of the new situation. Where many institutions have resorted to using applications from well-known international companies such as Microsoft that provide education platforms that provide electronic services that simulate the teaching environment and facilitate the teaching process, starting with video, conversation, recording, and various display tools, to share types of text and audio files and other services that facilitate communication between students and teachers. Since there were numerous studies that monitored the outcome of distance education and its effects on student achievement, but it should be noted here that most of them generally focused on equal opportunities and the availability of educational capabilities and infrastructure such as the availability of sufficient information, access to scientific material, the ability to understand and the development of skills. The number of university students registered in private and public Jordanian universities for the academic year (2019-2020) is about 326,910, according to the statistics of the Jordanian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. In the third week of the distance education experiment, the Ministry of Higher Education

launched an opinion poll on its platforms, and the result came as the Minister of Higher Education Abu Qadis stated that the general satisfaction rate among students ranged between 50% - 60%. The surveys initially focused on the various educational institutions' support for their teachers and students through the effectiveness of electronic platforms, and students' opinions about their educational institutions and their satisfaction. However, in this study, only the practical specialization subjects, which are described as applied, were highlighted. The researchers assumed equal opportunities among students in the major in terms of the presence of high-bandwidth Internet and assumed the existence of educational platforms of high quality. And teaching tools for materials, given that the design and visual communication specialization already requires the presence of high-quality tools and techniques suitable for the implementation of various projects. Where the study was conducted on teaching applied subjects by linking them to the real world and its possibilities from a distance. The Design Thinking approach focuses on developing students' creative confidence and links design thinking between real-world problem solving and classroom environments. Educators and students participate in practical design challenges that focus on:

- Develop empathy
- Work promotion
- Encourage thinking
- Develop Metacognition Awareness
- Promote problem-solving

During this iterative process, students are encouraged to: understand the user, challenge assumptions, and redefine problems. The essence of design thinking is the desire to improve products by analyzing and understanding how users interact with products and investigating the conditions in which they operate. This involves asking questions and challenging assumptions. Once students have questioned and investigated the circumstances of the problem, the process of generating solutions will help produce ideas that reflect the real limitations and aspects of that particular problem. Design Thinking provides a way to go deeper. It helps focus research, prototyping, and testing products and services to find new ways to improve a product, service, or design whereas Lindbergh et al. see, Design Thinking is not like any other method, as it allows freedom in choosing possibilities through a participatory process and team-based learning from different disciplines (Lindberg, Noysek&Meinl, 2010, p. 35.)

The importance of research

This research derives its importance from the researchers' desire to develop the effectiveness of distance learning of the applied type. The researchers propose teaching methods related to creative thinking curricula, such as design thinking, which will enhance and develop design students' skills in solving their problems instead of resorting to the teacher directly.

Theoretical importance

Monitoring the characteristics and consequences of remote teaching of applied sciences, which constitutes a scarcity of studies conducted in this regard.

Practical importance

This study is expected to come up with suggestions for applied methods that are effective in the field of design and visual communication.

Research objectives

Strengthening the reciprocity role of in the educational process in light of the pandemic, which would offer effective solutions from several angles instead of classical education methods as a boring or insufficient way to transmit information.

The limits of the study

The study was limited to the following:

- Sample of design and visual communication students at Jadara University.
- The educational levels of the students ranged between the second and third year, and their ages ranged between 18-22 years.
- The study was implemented in the second semester of the year 2020 AD.
- The study was applied to applied materials for the first year (advertising design).

Research problem

The problem lies in the gap between what the designer has learned and what must be learned remotely to meet the needs of the market and satisfy the desires of the beneficiaries. Where the Design Thinking strategy provides linking basic skills requirements to the academic field. It is also possible to build a real experience through real communication with customers, or to build a virtual experience aimed at education and building models that simulate reality.

Terminology of study

Design Thinking: It is a methodology based on finding solutions and innovation focused primarily on people. It is a five-step process of observation, visualization, prototyping, testing, and implementation. Design

thinking puts the people we design for at the center of the process and invites them to create tangible solutions. (<http://genfordev.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/design-thinking-un-development.pdf> , 2017, p. 7).

Distance education: Where the term distance education focused on the use of electronic means, including television and radio, however, in light of the pandemic, distance education was associated with the concept of e-education, and the focus was on the use of digital means based on Internet networks as a main means of communication, and where the definition can be summarized as follows: The use of multimedia that is included in the electronic medium from the Internet, e-mail, or conversation between two parties through international information networks (Al-Atrozi, Muhammad. On e-learning, 2020, pp. 17-18).

Study questions

This study attempts to answer the following main question: What is the effect of using design thinking through distance teaching of applied design and visual communication materials on students' skills and achievement?

Design thinking has five important "stages" - discovery, interpretation, reflection, experimentation, and development, and includes the following sub-questions:

- Does the curriculum contain real experience?
- Do all students participate in the educational process?
- Is a set of solutions being presented in different directions?
- In what ways are the effectiveness of solutions tested?
- Is there a relationship between the outputs of the applied subjects and the practice of the real profession?

Study hypotheses

- There is a statistically significant difference between the two research groups in the average cognitive level of students in the experimental groups on whom design thinking was used, and the control group that studied in the traditional way.

- There is a statistically significant difference between the average skills (number of realistic solutions) for the members of the two groups, the experimental groups on whom design thinking was used, and the control group that was studied in the traditional way.

- There is a statistically significant difference between the two research groups in the average level of students' competencies in terms of responsibility and autonomy in the experimental groups on whom design thinking was used, and the control group that was taught in the traditional way.

Research Methodology

The study relied on creating real experiments in project-based education. The researchers used the experimental method on a deliberate and controlled variable for the specific conditions of reality and the phenomenon with the intention of controlling behavior and the ability to predict (Sayed Abd al-Rahman, 2014, p. 91). Where the researchers relied on building the experiment by restructuring the study groups in order to reveal the impact and the role of each variable (Nibras Al-Mandalawi, 2016, p. 11). An independent variable is entered to measure the impact of the experiment, positively or negatively.

The Study Sample

The researchers relied on dividing the sample into two groups of students (first and second years) using two equal groups: (experimental group, control group) of 40 male and female students between the ages of (18-22) intentional samples for first, second and third year subjects, taking into account the homogeneity factor when selecting the sample between the two groups in terms of: (stages of the study, age, gender) in order to ensure the possibility of dimensional comparisons between the two groups.

Age: The average age of the experimental group was 14.33 years with a standard deviation of 0.651, while the arithmetic average of the control group was 14.25 with a standard deviation of 0.621 The researcher used the Mann-Whitney test to examine the significance of the differences between the two groups: ($u = 66.50$).

It is not statistically significant, which confirms the homogeneity of the two groups in age.

Study stages: The researchers conducted a Mann-Whitney test to examine the significance of the differences between the averages of the experimental and control groups in the degree of behavioral problems on the pre-test.

Study variables: The study consisted of independent and dependent variables as follows:

The independent variable: the proposed project based on design thinking.

Dependent variable: Students' interaction and offering flexible and creative solutions in a hypothetical environment.

Previous studies

Numerous studies that have discussed the concept of e-learning and its various ways in foreign countries before the spread of Corona pandemic, and some Arab studies concerned with this kind of education in the Arab countries, which have had many special treatises on this subject, as a means of learning, and with the spread of a pandemic Corona, there have been numerous studies on the development of the form of

education and the need for the whole world to research the development of this type of learning, especially with the spread of technologies and the remarkable improvement in the Internet and its recent development.

The study of Harmelia (2021) confirmed that there is a significant increase in the promotion of students' learning independence, it was noted that 65% of students stated that they were more active in completing class assignments and searching for improvement courses through e-learning.

While Yang (2021) in his study reported that students evaluated the online learning experience at an Irish university, most students still preferred in-class learning, despite some very positive online learning experiences, they felt that the social aspect and benefit from learning and face-to-face interaction with trainers and peers could not be fully emulated in an online learning environment, as the results indicate the foundation for an effective online learning experience is participation.

Tantawi (2020) stressed the importance of e-learning as an urgent necessity imposed by the Corona pandemic that swept the whole world, and indeed a number of universities around the world were able to utilize the potential of e-learning, as a means of e-learning, providing scientific content for students characteristically attractive and through a variety of teaching methods, based on sound and image together, which enhances the effectiveness of the students and give them the necessary skills, and makes them more able to innovate and think of modern methods of verification policies and strategies for sustainable education, which contributed to the increase in education efficiency and its application in an interactive and virtual manner with students.

Melles (2010) study was conducted on 90 students at Swinburne University studying simultaneously in Melbourne and Hong Kong in the first semester of 2011, where a course in design thinking was implemented as a curriculum through discussions and special workshops, students were asked to implement projects on campus by attending lectures, blog discussions, reviewing literature and collecting notes, the study found it difficult to train design specialists, such as interior and industrial designers for the first time, as the problem was seen as a design idea or a product rather than an integrated system that has several aspects, the essence of which is the human being.

Dym et al. (2005) conducted a study in which design thinking was reviewed as a mechanism to access knowledge assets, where the student becomes a design researcher while identifying the design to reach how to do this for design through making statistics of possibilities, estimates and experiments, in the sense of building a conceptual understanding of the knowledge field.

Oxman (1999) in her study of architecture at the Israel Institute of Technology in Haifa, she advocated cognitive orientation through design thinking and as a basis for learning design through the web-pad is based on the student's exploration of the concept of the problem and the formulation of cognitive structures that relate to potential solution spaces in the middle of conceptual drawings, where the interaction between student and teacher becomes more than just a participatory process, the process becomes dialectical learning. Oxman proposed a learning framework in which knowledge is acquired by organizing and developing conceptual structures in the form of a thinking map in the constructivist learning model by providing a tool for organizing and representing knowledge. And in the nineties of the last century in 1996, Moore & Kearsley developed the concept and linked it to the existence of a technological communication channel to facilitate interaction between teachers and students and the availability of electronic materials to support learners. (Moore & Kearsley, 1996, pp.179).

While Holmberg (1977) presented in his study an expanded definition of distance education: It is all stages of study and all educational stages without direct supervision, but subject to the process of planning, organizing and directing by an educational institution and teachers (Alaa Sadiq, 2004), it was also known as open education, where the student studies without being restricted by walls and study chairs, and with it the student depends on himself through correspondence. Where open education was a solution to many constraints, and as confirmed by the British Commonwealth Council as those opportunities that were given to the learner to choose the means, place, time and duration of study, and grouping them with educational media, and opportunities for open education increased with the presence of technology and the Internet, where correspondences were facilitated, as confirmed by UNESCO in its reports during the pandemic (Khaled Salah Hanafi Mahmoud, 2014, p. 10). Attempts to study distance education in the past have produced models for classifying and describing technology media associated with distance learning, the most famous of which is the ACTIONS model (pp307-264, 2015, Bates) presented by Bates 1995, where letters symbolize the following terms, respectively: (Access, Costs, Teaching & Learning, Interactivity & user-friendliness, Organizational issues, Novelty, speed). And choosing the appropriate teaching aids has several benefits that are positively reflected on the educational return of the student. These, in turn, depend on the effectiveness of the content of the teaching process, which is linked to the teacher, the recipient, the subject, the learning structure, the general influences on teaching and decision-making (Saleh Abdel Aziz, 1969, 33). And with the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic (Coronavirus), teachers are being asked to create learning environments that are highly inclusive, based on finding solutions and innovation. According to Design Thinking, tool observation, experience, and query allow designers to understand human needs and shape information through an awareness

of experience (Skaggs, 2018). Whereas the term design thinking included more than one point of view that focused on the aspects of innovation and a concept that focused on the human being and his needs, two basic practices that focus on two different aspects, namely (Goldschmidt, 2017):

- Descriptive models based on observation through reality
- An applied model through which institutions and companies seek to provide innovations in the field of products and commodities.

Researchers seek to conduct realistic experiences through augmented reality, and seek interaction from students by promoting opinions and share solutions remotely.

Nigel Cross (2001) in his study entitled "Designedly ways of knowing: design discipline versus design science" Unravelling the conflict that began to emerge in the early 1960s when attempts to "science" was made "design, bring the field within the objective of rational sciences. Cross highlights statements by radical technologist Buckminster Fuller, in which he referred to the "science of design decade" requiring a collaborative approach that includes a deep understanding of human beings, he suggested that "design science" could form fundamental common ground, intellectual pursuit, and communication across the arts, sciences, and technology. What is suggested that the study of design can be an accessible interdisciplinary study for everyone.

The Experiment

The experiment was applied to students among second and third year students in the subject of advertising, according to the description provided by the Graphic Design Department of Jadara University: This course aims to identify the foundations and considerations on which the design of the advertising medium is based, while employing those foundations and rules in designing the various posters that are displayed in roads, means of transportation, shops, institutions and companies, as well as studying the methods of providing periodic information to various institutions and bodies and the public dealing with a commodity, product or service through the design of daily correspondence paper, envelopes, covers and annual calendar. Materials are evaluated according to quality requirements and based on the theory of bloom taxonomy 1956 into three levels as follows:

Table 1: Approved evaluation methodology for the subject at Jadara University (Department of Design and Visual Communication)

Knowledge	skills	Competencies
A1-Theoretical Understanding	B1 - General problem solving and analytical skills	-C1 Autonomy, responsibility and context
K1- Be aware of customer requirements	S1- To analyze the problem into its primary elements	C1- To be creative by coming up with new and unrepitive ideas
A2- practical application	B2 - Telecommunications, Information Technology, Communications and Computers	C2 - to anticipate the most appropriate solutions to the problem.
K2- To apply the principles of design.	S2- The work must be done using technology	

Based on the prior evaluation, the students were subjected to a two-week experiment, where a realistic idea was put forward by designing the logo for the university's cultural café.

The researchers divided the students into two groups: 20 male/female students equally (gender, age, school stage).

When the idea of the logo for the cultural café that will be established at the university was presented as a realistic model, the students were asked to divide into two groups of 10 people and give ideas for designing a logo that was not specified with a specific number.

Control group: The students were divided into two groups, then an introduction was given about the café, its objectives and components, and the request was made to proceed with the design as usual.

The experimental group: The two groups of students in the first stage were asked to build their perceptions about the café as the control group, then two students from each group were asked to discuss the topic and put their perceptions about the café in the form of drawings, questions and notes, then the students were asked to discuss remotely students from different disciplines about the café, determine the students' desires through the café and build proposals, then they were asked to add modifications, build observations, build a prototype and test it with the students if they are desirable from the users' point of view.

Analysis of the results

Table 2: Results of the control group based on the approved evaluation of the subject at Jadara University (Department of Design and Visual Communication)

Certified results	Tools and techniques	Achieved results
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	used	A K1	K2	B S1	S2	C C1	C2
		5	5	5	5	5	5
The first experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	3	3	2	4	3	2
The second experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	2	4	1	3	1	1
The third experience	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	1	3	1	4	1	1
The fourth experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	2	2	1	4	1	1
The fifth experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	2	4	1	4	2	1
The sixth experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	1	3	1	4	1	2
The seventh Experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	2	2	1	4	1	2

The second group (experimental)

Table 3: The results of the experimental group based on the approved evaluation of the subject at Jadara University (Department of Design and Visual Communication)

Logo for a cultural café at the university	Tools and techniques used	Achieved results					
		A K1	K2	B S1	S2	C C1	C2
The first experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	3	4	4	4	4	3
The second experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	4	4	3	3	4	3
The third experience	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	3	3	3	3	3	2
The fourth experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	4	3	4	4	4	3
The fifth experiment	Notes, pencil sketches, application in a program	2	2	3	4	2	3

Hypothesis testing

- The first hypothesis: There is a statistically significant difference between the two research groups in the average level of knowledge of students in the experimental groups who used design thinking and the control group who studied in the traditional way.

The hypothesis was tested using independent t-tests.

Table 4: results of the first hypothesis

Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig
control group	2.4286	.53452	0.04
experimental group	3.2000	.75829	

The results show that the significance value is (0.04), which shows that there are statistically significant differences in the average level of knowledge in favor of the experimental group (3.2).

- The second hypothesis: There is a statistically significant difference between the average skills (number of realistic solutions) for the members of the two groups, the experimental groups on whom design thinking was used, and the control group that was taught in the traditional way. The hypothesis was tested using independent t-tests.

Table 5: results of the second hypothesis

Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig
Control group	2.5000	.28868	0.01
Experimental group	3.5000	.50000	

The results show that the significance value is (0.01), which shows that there are statistically significant differences in the average skill level in favor of the experimental group (3.5).

- The third hypothesis: There is a statistically significant difference between the two research groups in the average level of students' competencies in terms of responsibility and autonomy in the experimental groups on whom design thinking was used, and the control group that studied in the traditional way. The hypothesis was tested using independent t-tests.

Table 6: results of the third hypothesis

Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig
Control group	1.4286	.53452	0.00
Experimental group	3.1000	.54772	

The results show that the significance value is (0.01), which shows that there are statistically significant differences in the average level of competencies in favor of the experimental group (3.1).

Results discussion

The researchers found that the remote design thinking process encountered difficulties in terms of communicating with the work environment and the beneficiaries, as the prototypes were discussed with people with difficulty due to the lack of a mechanism for communication between students between each other through the applications and the official website of the university. And they were reached in personal ways, which prompted the researchers to recommend to repeat the experiment, but with greater stability, and where the results reached by the experimental group required attention and the results were as follows:

- Regarding the first hypothesis, the researchers concluded that there are statistically significant differences between the cognitive level of students who have complete knowledge of the client and the group that does not value communication means.
- Regarding the second hypothesis. And that the average number of solutions for students who applied design thinking is greater than the average of the group that studied in the traditional way.
- Regarding the third hypothesis, the researchers concluded that there are statistically significant differences in the effect of design thinking on generating good ideas.
- This indicates that the group of students to whom design thinking was applied took more time to determine decisions and built their results according to customer knowledge than the other group who applied the traditional methods to them.

Conclusion

Although modern education systems, especially distance education, e-learning and blended hybrid education, have become a major concern in various countries of the world, and many seek to launch professional electronic platforms that help take advantage of these systems; However, every country should study well the extent to which these systems can be applied to its pupils, students and teachers, and try to qualify and train them well to deal with them first before actually starting the application, especially since the inability to use these systems by any member of the educational process will return of course, with a negative return that is completely devoid of any significant benefit.

In conclusion, it must be noted that the near future will witness a radical change in the current educational systems as a whole, and therefore; Each country must immediately develop its own educational development plan in order to be able to meet the challenges and provide education requirements in the near future.

Recommendations

When we talk about education and its prosperity, and thus the amount of services provided by educational institutions to their students and the extent of their satisfaction, and this requires highly accurate strategies and plans that aim towards development and positive change. And since the education sector is and is

still the standard for the progress of societies, this required investment in knowledge and scientific research, especially with the growth of new professional industries that require high specifications that depend on education based on discovery, investigation, analysis and conclusion, and this necessitates diversification in the sources and forms of knowledge, and based on the research departments (teacher qualification, teaching methods and curricula, availability of tools and the appropriate environment), some measures must be taken into account in the future.

1. Defining clear standards for the quality of e-learning.
2. Qualifying the human cadre (administrators, students and learners) to use advanced applications in e-learning.
3. Providing an environment that simulates education laboratories, such as the presence of an appropriate “home studio” for teaching various applied courses.
4. The use of applications that provide tools and materials that are difficult to obtain and that will facilitate the process of communicating information to the student, which is known as “Augmented Reality”.
5. Using teaching methods that focus on dialogue and exchange, such as design thinking.

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